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When there is nothing to hear. Reflections on microscopic hearing on the threshold of silence.

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Abstract

Although the use of silence is of importance when defining the grammatical properties (punctuation and structuring) of musical discourse, a more accurate study results from the observation of silence beyond this context, that is, of silence as a limit. This paper seeks to reflect on the ideas of silence as a utopia and auditory threshold as a generator of a type of perception of microscopic characteristics. To deepen this direction, we will review a set of concepts that will allow us to make a synthetic vision of the potential existing in the ideas outlined above. Specifically, we will refer to the statements of Vladimir Jankélévitch (2003 [1961]) about the "differential properties" of a silence understood as attenuation, and of absolute silence as an "inconceivable limit"; to John Cage (2002 [1961]; Pritchett 1996) regarding silence as the enabler of an emergent listening of ambient sound, of discrete characteristics; to David Toop (2016 [2010]), in particular when it refers to the problem of mediation/acute perception that silent media make possible; and to Brandon LaBelle (2012 [2008]), regarding the inevitability of a relational ecology of hearing; these, among other approaches. We will also refer to the oriental concepts of *ma* (Pilgram 1986) and *wu-wei* (Tse & Soubllette, 1990), which state the existence of silence as emptiness. The document, although not conclusive, proposes that the field that encourages electroacoustic music can open up vast possibilities for the performance of an audition of discrete (barely audible) characteristics. Thus allowing, through the use of the loudspeaker as a technological prosthesis, what we well might call a type of "hearing at the threshold of hearing," or more precisely, a "microscopic hearing."

When there is nothing to hear,
so much starts to sound.
Silence is not the absence of sound
but the beginning of listening,
(Voegelin 2010: 83)

Silence and (Im)mobility

According to Henri Bergson, immobility, understood as the absence of movement, would not exist, but rather a situation of relativity in which existing mobility would be imperceptible. Bergson exemplifies the hypothetical case of two trains traveling in the same direction and at the same speed; this would allow passengers of one of the trains to perceive the neighboring train as motionless. It would be then “a certain regulating of mobility on mobility which produces the effect of immobility” (Bergson 1946 [1934]: 184). Consequently, and in keeping with Bergson, “there never is real immobility, if we understand by that an absence of movement. Movement is reality itself...” (*op. cit.*: 168).

The above applies to the field of sound as a physical movement. And as with Bergson trains, it will be the correspondence with the environment that will define what is really (or not) heard. Therefore, we can also affirm that there is no "true silence." The threshold of auditory perception would be, in the words of Vladimir Jankélévitch, an "inconceivable limit":

[S]ilence is, after all, not nothingness. Absolute silence, like pure space or bare time, is an inconceivable limit. (...) Nothingness, one might say, has no properties. (...) Two nothings are only a single, same nothing, a single same zero. But silence has differential properties: and as a result, this particular nothingness is not nothing at all (...). (Jankélévitch 2003 [1961]: 136-7)

From the above, we can infer that there is something to listen to when we talk about silence and that we can apprehend its "differential properties" through a liminal listening that allows access to that "inconceivable limit." Thus, musical silence would not be emptiness or

cessation but attenuation. Because an "attenuation of intensity it is at the threshold of the inaudible, a game played with almost-nothing" (*op. cit.*: 142). It would be about an "infinitesimal sound," a "micromusic" (*op. cit.*: 143). As Jankélévitch himself indicates, "[t]o seek silence is to seek a meta-empirical Beyond, a supersensory realm more essential by far than the realm occupied by existence, which roars at high volume, with a booming voice" (*op. cit.*: 145). This micromusic would have an infinite propagation, because, such as Jean-Luc Nancy poses, the resonance available to silence calls for a transit that goes from the phenomenological subject to a resonant other. That is, "an intensive spacing of a rebound that does not end in any return to self without immediately relaunching, as an echo, a call to that same self" (Nancy 2007: 21). The resonance of silence thus conceived would have not only reflective characteristics but also productive and multiplicative ones. It would be the infinitesimal sound in all its infinity.

4'33''

And if we talk about silence, we cannot forget John Cage and his consideration of this concept as a generator and bearer of music. In his 4'33", work that gets its name from the accumulation of silences that as a whole last that amount of time, by using the "classical" music concert convention for the exhibition of these silences (that is, considering a silent listening by the audience), puts on stage exactly the utopian dimension of silence. And this never comes, because its search is continuously interrupted by ambient sounds in or out of the concert hall. Cage himself spoke of how silence open "the doors of the music to the sounds that happen to be in the environment", concluding that "[t]here is no such thing as an empty space or an empty time" since "[t]here is always something to see, something to hear. (Cage 1961: 8). We should note that, according to James Pritchett, the origins of the reflection proposed by 4'33" regarding silence "lie not in Cage's Works of the 1950s and 60s, but rather in the aesthetic milieu" (Pritchett 1993: 59). This latter propitiated by his *Lecture of Nothing*, held at the Artists Club in New York in 1950, two years before the premiere of 4'33" in Woodstock. Here below an appointment of this conference:

I am here , and there is nothing to say . (...) I have nothing to say
And I am saying it and that is
poetry as I need it .
This space of time is organized
We need not to fear these silences, -
(Cage 1961: 109).

Here, it is the artistic action (musical in 4'33'', poetic in *Lecture of Nothing*) that allows us to aim for silence, declaring it and at the same time, granting its existence. This statement encourages itself to say the unspeakable. It is interesting that the silence that Cage thus poses would not exist only in the sound field, or in the musical one, but above all in an ontological dimension.

Expanded hearing

On the other hand, it is interesting to note what happens with hearing in the thresholds of the silent. In this regard, David Toop tells us that when “silence and other modalities of auditory phenomena are represented through ‘silent’ media, this association of mediumship becomes more acute” (Toop 2010: viii). That is, a silent medium would allow an expansion of perception. Besides, silence could be understood as “those microscopic sounds, atmospheres and minimal acoustic environments” (*op. cit.*: xi) that emerge with intense listening. We would be in presence, then, of a silent hearing microscopy.

An example of the exploration of these limits is that addressed by the "Sound Museum of Silence"¹. This project, as musicologist Ana María Ochoa explains, is a website where anyone can contribute with "silent recordings", proposing for this to consider the 20 db threshold as a reference. In consequence, "[t]he perception of this soundscape depends on the use of electronic amplification devices. (...) Here, the limits of human hearing are simultaneously highlighted and transformed through technological prosthetics" (Ochoa 2015: 185). It should

¹ <http://20decibel.blogspot.com/>

be noted then that this prosthetic liminal hearing (speakers, headphones, sound displays, etc.) would be located in the territory of technological post-human. Technological advances have allowed us to modify the relationship between body (and its thresholds) and matter (in this case, sound matter). This medium provides access to a "universe of possibilities that technology offers to a body that, in the union of meat and metal, promises a radical renewal of the subjective experience of the world and of life"² (Mejía 2005: 15). Thus, this particular liminal audition embodied in the project "Sound Museum of Silence" allows absorbing the listening of that "infinitesimal sound" that Jankélévitch speaks. This latter, through a process of unveiling that we could call "technological post-human micromusical"; this would naturally fall below the thresholds of human perception, transforming our auditory experience in a categorically way.

It follows from the previous example that the broad and diverse field of creative possibilities that electroacoustic music provides (through the loudspeaker) in its exaggeratedly discrete (barely audible) and spatially multiple sound dimensions for the development of a "hearing at the threshold of audition ", represents a prolific terrain for the exploration of the utopia of silence. But what does it mean more precisely that music, particularly of the electroacoustic type, manifests itself as a barely audible sound dimension?

Technology of Silence

First, it is crucial to consider the characteristics of the envelope of the sound (s) that make up this discrete music. According to what Peter Heil and his collaborators raise in the chapter "A probabilistic model of absolute auditory thresholds and its possible physiological basis", from the book "Basic Aspects of Hearing" (2013), hearing thresholds not only depend on the temporal envelope of the stimulus but also decrease as the duration of the stimulus increases. That is, the more long sustain, the less auditory detection. Moreover, there is the phenomenon that was stated by Francisco Cervantes Constantino (*et al.*) in the same book just cited in the chapter "The Role of Sensitivity to Transients in the Detection of Appearing and Disappearing Objects in Complex." This study proposes, among other things, that sudden

² ... un universo de posibilidades que la tecnología ofrece a un cuerpo que, en la unión de la carne y el metal, promete una renovación radical de la experiencia subjetiva del mundo y de la vida.

attacks are fundamental in the perception of sound, and that cutting these attacks directly compromises this perception. Therefore, we can conclude that the sounds that are most useful for provoking a microscopic hearing are those of ample sustain and a rather flat attack.

A second aspect to consider is that of the pitch or frequency. We know that the range of human perception extends between 20 hz and 20 khz. Under this range, there is infrasound, and over this, ultrasound. But also, “[i]n the frequency range between 2 and 5 kHz almost every subject with normal hearing exhibits a very sensitive range in which very small sound pressure levels below 0 dB are reached” (Fastl & Zwicker 2006: 20). This latter implies that the range between 2 and 5 kHz represents a very stable range and the most audible at very discrete intensities. This frequency range represents an exciting working territory of sound microscopy, possible to be explored quite accurately by electroacoustic music.

On the other hand, the world of infrasonic sounds opens up fascinating possibilities. Indeed, in this region, there is a sensory transmutation, from the auditory to the tactile. Australian composer Cat Hope has made stimulating explorations in this regard. She considers the existence of an infrasonic music “[w]here music engages sounds that move below tonal recognition and can encourage the listener to seek other sensations as a way to experience that sound (...). These different ways to experience sound offer the possibility to create music such that the entire body, rather than the ear alone, can be active in the listening experience” (Hope 2009: 52). However, we face the problem that the vast majority of full-range loudspeakers usually respond from 40 hz. up, and sub-woofers typically from 20 hz. There are, however, some specific transducers that resolve frequencies below 20 hz. If we consider these devices, electroacoustic music can assume the creation of infrasonic music. This latter calls into question the idea that music can only be heard, or in other words, the existence of an exclusively sound-based music.

As for the intensity, we have already mentioned the limit of 20 db as the reference threshold. However, this limit seems to be the most unstable of all. First, because, as we have already seen, the different audible frequencies require different intensities to be heard, being a stable range only that which is between 1,000 and 5,000 hz. Second, because the decibel indicates a referential link to another magnitude: the lowest auditory threshold in humans, which is indicated as 0 db. And this threshold is variable, depending on the age, the level of wear of

the auditory system, and the particular physiological characteristics of the individual. Also, and as Julian Perez Porto and Ana Gardey indicate, “a listener is not able to reliably indicate the intensity of the same sound if he hears it more than once, although he is able to compare this property between two different sounds”³ (Pérez & Gardey 2017). In other words, the human hearing has such complex psychoacoustic characteristics that it is entirely possible that two equal sounds, with the same intensity, are heard as if they had different intensities.

Besides, sound, and particularly sound at the threshold of the audible, necessarily implies a contextualized perceptual action in a very concrete and material dimension: space. In this regard, it is necessary to consider a relational ecology of hearing.

Sound is intrinsically and unignorably relational: it emanates, propagates, communicates, vibrates, and agitates; it leaves a body and enters others; (...) [i]t is my view that sound’s relational condition can be traced through modes of spatiality, for sound and space in particular have a dynamic relationship. This no doubt, stands at the core of the very practice of sound art—the activation of the existing relation between sound and space. (LaBelle 2012 [2008], 468-9)

Brandon LaBelle also reminds us of the social dimension of sound, because when it exists, it generates auditors who, in turn, exercise their listening. And since sound is multi-spatial (it exists in many places at the same time), there would be a wide variety of listening points, and therefore of people located at these points. This mapping would allow multiple perceptions, obtained from the particular qualities of each place of sound existence. And consequently, the multiplication and diversification of hearing thresholds through the mediation of the loudspeaker in its ecological context. The sagacity of liminal hearing in this context is of formidable potential, and only partially explored.

In addition to the above, we should not forget that the sound space is primarily mental and that auditory accuracy at the spatial level will depend mainly on the will and context of that spatial listening. For example, and as Peter Damaske points out in his book “*Acoustics and Hearing*”, “[t]he space between [two] loudspeakers is filled by phantom sources, as they are

³ Un oyente no es capaz de indicar de una manera fiable la intensidad de un mismo sonido si lo escucha más de una vez, aunque sí es capaz de comparar esta propiedad entre dos sonidos diferentes.

called, created by the data processing in the brain” (Damaske 2008: 5). The same is stated by Michel Chion when he refers to what he calls the spatial magnetization of sound by image: “When we perceive a sound as being offscreen or located at screen right this is a psychological phenomenon” (Chion 1993 [1990]: 70). In summary, the threshold of hearing will also depend both on the ecological dimension of liminal sounds, and on the psychological processing that is produced as a result of their spatial characteristics.

Mind and silence

Finally, it is interesting to note that a particular conception of silence in the dissolution of the boundaries between silence and sound, and in general of the "binary logic of apparently opposite forces"⁴ (Ochoa 2017: 121), is related to the Japanese idea of *ma*. This idea can mean interval, gap, opening, space between, time between. In this sense, *ma* would contain the emptiness that generates the perceptible everything.

In the distinction between *mu* (nothing, no, nonbeing) and *u* (something, being, existence), for example, the importance of *mu* as the ground or basis for all existence is clear. In fact, to be awake to *mu* is to be liberated in *u*. (...) Much like the *Tao te ching*, it is thus by virtue of nothing that something is fulfilled or used (Pilgram 1986: 265)

This concept of emptiness is also developed in the *Tao te ching*, the cornerstone of Taoist philosophy, written by Lao Tse in the sixth century BC. This book indicates in its epigram XI the following:

Thirty spokes converge on the hub of a Wheel
but it is from its emptiness that the utility of the carriage depends.
Modeling the clay the vessels are made
but it is from its emptiness that the utility of the vessel depends.
(...)
In consequence

⁴ lógica binaria de fuerzas aparentemente opuestas

just as we benefit from what it is

we must recognize the <http://nave.io/residencias/tacito/usefulness> of what is not⁵. (Tse & Soubllette, 1990: 56)

That is, it would be in non-being (*wu-wei*) that being would have its existence. In this sense, *ma* can be understood as a manifestation of *wu-wei*. Or said in more western terms, it is not in another place than in the emptiness of silence that sound has existence. A potential, but also literal existence. For when there is nothing to listen to, a type of music emerges with powerful strength that we can access through a microscopic hearing, an audition on the infinite threshold of silence.

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⁵ Treinta rayos convergen en el cubo de una rueda / pero es de su vacío que depende la utilidad del carro. / Modelando la arcilla se hacen vasijas / pero es de su vacío que depende la utilidad de la vasija. / (...) En consecuencia / así como nos beneficiamos con lo que es / debemos reconocer la utilidad de lo que no es.

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